

QUESTIONING AS AN EFFECTIVE TOOL OF TEACHING ENGLISH POETRY

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ABSTRACT

Teaching poetry requires lecturers to use a variety of strategies, techniques and tools to support students in the process of studying, and one of the most widely used strategies is questioning. Methodological studies conducted by many pedagogues have mirrored the positive effects of questioning in the learning process. Questioning develops students critical thinking and creative thinking. The aim of the paper is to implement 'questioning' as a tool of teaching English poetry. Questioning opens the doors and the Armenian students can read and understand poetry both in horizontal and vertical contexts.

The information presented in this paper has been collected through the course of teaching 'English literature' at State University of Shirak, RA.

In relation to results, the majority of students recognize and emphasize the positive impact of adequately applying questioning in teaching English poetry. This tool enhances students' reading and speaking skills.

Keywords: method, poetry, literature, field work, question, answer, song, text.

*Poetry is the spontaneous overflow of powerful feelings:
it takes its origin from emotion recollected in tranquility*
William Wordsworth

The present paper touches upon the method of questioning in teaching English poetry. It is common knowledge that questioning as a key tool is used in different disciplines. We aim to present the role of the above-mentioned method in teaching English poetry in the context of two English romantic writers- William Blake's and William Wordsworth's poetry.

The educational process requires the teacher to consider the student as the center of the instructional process. This student-centered approach encompasses shifting the focus of instruction from the teacher to the student. That means moving from a traditional perspective of teaching to one in which students are able to construct knowledge by themselves, with their teacher's support. In this construction of knowledge, students should be the ones that interact, talk, and debate or discuss in the classroom most of the time; however, it does not happen in real life. Teachers are the ones who are always talking during the instructional process (Wangru, 2016). Most methods of classroom teaching are based on questioning (Gall, 1970). Teaching of poetry is not an easy activity.

According to Kennedy and Gioia, "Poems state ideas... and sometimes the ideas are invaluable, and yet the most impressive idea in the world will not make a poem, unless its words are selected and arranged with loving art".

The English give the following definition of the word "poetry":

- ❖ 1. The act or practice of composing poems.
- 2. a. Poems regarded as forming a division of literature.
- b. The poetic works of a given author, dictionaries group, nation, or kind.
- 3. Literature written in meter; verse.
- 4. Prose that resembles a poem in some respect, as in vivid imagery or rhythmic sound.

5. The essence or characteristic quality of a poem: "It is impossible to separate the 'poetry' in Paradise Lost from the peculiar doctrines that it enshrines" (T.S. Eliot).

6. A quality that suggests poetry, as in grace, beauty, or harmony: *the poetry of the dancer's movements*.

(<https://www.thefreedictionary.com/poetry>)

The study was carried out in the course of teaching English literature for Shirak State University 3rd year students.

Before moving on to our survey, let us take a look at some of the methods of teaching poetry.

According to the book entitled as *The Art of Teaching Poetry*, the following methods are mainly singled out:

1. Teaching Tone and Mood (Tone is the author's feelings within the poem; Mood is the way the readers feel when they read the poem).
2. Poetry as a Song (Students can really get into the poetry lesson by creating a musical beat for a poem).
3. Activate Prior Knowledge (Students are more receptive to new learning when they connect it to what they already know).
4. Establish Theme (Teaching with a theme and its accompanying guiding questions is not new to most of us..)
5. Focus on Facts (Creating poetry is a wonderful way..)
6. Dramatize a poem, Set a Scene, etc...(Shrivastava, *The Art of Teaching Poetry*, Prowess Publishing, 2019).

For carrying out the research we have interviewed 30 students on the challenges of English poetry (The questions were asked after having studied English romantic poets' works in the auditorium). The questions were as follows:

1. Do you find English poetry difficult? And if the answer is yes, please mention some of them.
2. How can we overcome the difficulty of analyzing and illustrating poetry?

20 students mentioned that at first glance English poetry seemed difficult for digesting the content, but in the course of time they managed to get accustomed to learning and loving poetry via question making and asking. One of the reasons of avoiding poetry learning,

was the students' narrative daily thinking. Let's present the students' answer on the difficulties of William Blake's and William Wordsworth's poetry in a graphical way:

As far as the second question is concerned, the students gave preference to Question and Answer Format in Learning Poetry.

Diiferent types of questions were asked while teaching Blake's and Wordsworth's poetry.

At first the poets' poems were read and afterwards questions were followed. We shall introduce the questionnaire that included both our self-made questions and the textbook questions.

The questions were asked after having studied the works of two English poets.

Questionnaire

What comes to your mind when you hear the word "romantic"
Have you ever heard on the literary movement of <i>Romanticism</i> with special reference to English period?
W. Blake and W. Wordsworth created their poetic masterpieces in the light of Romanticism. Can you describe the mentioned idea?
Can you highlight your mood when you read the titles of W. Blake's lyrics (Songs of Innocence "Infant Joy", "The Little Black Boy", "A Cradle Song", Laughing Song", "the Chimney Sweeper", "Lamb", Songs of Experience: "Holy Thursday", "The Tyger", "The Little Boy Lost").
Is it easy to make a borderline between Blake's the series "Songs of Innocence" and "Songs of Experience"

Taking into account the limited format of the article, we present the students' answers in a brief way.

1. I liked the poem *Lamb* before reading it, when I just read the title it seemed to me that it was a childish work, but when I read it my thoughts and ideas completely changed. It is a very mature and interesting work that describes the delicacy and purity with a very unique approach, associating it with a lamb and giving beautiful comparisons, the poem attracts the reader even more. When you read the poem, you imagine a little innocent girl hugging a little lamb.(interviewee: student Mariam Harutyunyan, 3rd year student, Faculty of Humanities, Shirak State University).

Interviewee: Siranush Hovhannisyan

In William Blake's poetry there are many outstanding verses but the one that stresses importance is "The Chimney Sweeper". The first two lines are especially emotional: "When my mother died I was very young and my father sold me yet my tongue"

They convey a plethora of feelings to the reader and lead to its logical continuation, where there are a lot of people sharing the same destiny.

As to its metaphorical features we see that Blake compares little Tom Dacres hair with the curled hair of a lamb, thus showing his innocence as a child. In the other line, the dream, in which an angel came and set them free from the black coffins and the following

scene in the nature are also of great metaphorical importance. Nature shows their desire to be free all they desire is to be in a natural environment in which they have never been. It is a dream because it is too far from their own reality, which is full of sufferings.

Before reading the verse I thought it might be about an adult who is a poor chimney sweeper and works hard to make the ends meet. After reading it I have mixed feelings concerning the whole concept maybe because I have distinct feelings about children and their childhood in general.

The last stanza has the following line:

"So if all do their duty, they need not fear harm"

After the dreamy and romantic lines Blake brings us back to the harsh reality in which the chimney sweepers live.

Yeganyan Lilit

"The Chimney Sweeper" is a poem by William Blake, published in the collection "Songs of Innocence". This verse has really touched my heart as it tells about the boy who has been sold by his father to sweep chimneys. The scene, in which the new boy named Tom Dacre arrived and cried because his curly lamb-like hair was shaved off, made me cry. I immediately imagined the scene and it touched my inner world.

I would like to introduce my expectations before reading the verse.

Firstly when I read the title Chimney Sweeper I thought that the hero was going to be an elder man with a tired face. I had never expected to have a small child

for that kind of work. So it was very surprising for me. I thought it was going to be about the difficulties of that time that adults were facing, but not the children.

So now let me express my emotions after reading the verse. This verse is a kind of masterpiece for me. Let me explain why it is so. It introduces all the problems that existed during that period of time. Also it refers to the problem that is urgent even nowadays. That is child labour. Many poor children did not have the opportunity to go to school and live a normal life. Many of them passed through different pains and difficulties. These lines are great evidence of it. They made me feel the pain that Tom Dacre experienced:

There's little Tom Dacre, who cried when his head
That curled like a lamb's back, was shaved, so I
said,.....

Let's pay attention to the word 'lamb' which is a symbol of innocence as we know. So the child is compared with a lamb described as an innocent creature. Due to the great author William Blake we are able to see the main issues of those times, that is how that many innocent children became the victims of the inequality and injustice.

When I read the verse these concepts came to my mind:

- CHILD LABOUR
- INEQUALITY
- INJUSTICE
- HARDSHIPS

INJUSTICE

Now it's turn to represent the eye-catching lines giving the main idea of the verse;

Then down a green plain, leaping, laughing they run,
And wash in a river and shine in the Sun.

This section of the poem effectively represents the kind of behavior that boys of that age should be occupied – not sweeping others' chimneys. That is a kind of instinct for children to have carefree childhood.

Let me talk about the author William Blake. Before getting acquainted with his work I never expected to be so much impressed. Besides these topics he perfectly shows the nature and its details in a way that you want to be close to it as much as possible.

ODA

Why are you hiding the place where the sky and water end?

What secret have you hidden there?

Maybe you don't want me to be there,

With one hand patting the water drops and

With another hand catching the sunlight to warm my soul.

Or you want to show your strength

Strength that nobody owes but you

To mix everything when you want

As you do with our souls.

Vardanyan Anichka

Sleep, sleep beauty bright...

The child is described as the brightest beauty, a mild angel, a happy child, a sweet babe, and a holy image.

Before getting acquainted with the poem I imagined a mother sitting next to her newborn baby and singing this lullaby. (If you try singing you will like it especially the alliteration "ess" "shhh")

I can hear the child's innocent and pure voice- being happy to listen to the sweet words that her mother

is saying and the melody the toy plays hanging on the baby bed. I even smelt the odor of a newborn baby which can't be compared to anything.

After reading and analyzing the poem you understand how deep it is.

"Songs of Innocence" - who is the most innocent creature of this world, of course, a newborn child.

The poem shows the mother's concern over the child's journey from innocence to experience. You start wondering how a child (mankind) changes during his/her life. I imagined the same picture but now the child is lying next to his/her mature life and mature self.

How different they are ...

The poem is thought-provoking how a man can write a lullaby (we associate lullabies with mother's who tell sweet, calming, pacifying words to their child)

It describes a simple lullaby through which I see Jesus Christ who was innocent as a child.

Twinkle twinkle little star how I wonder what you are...

Instead of hanging toys I see the words - moon, soft, sweet, heavenly face, peace.

“The Tiger”

The work by William Blake that stresses importance is “The Tiger”. This work is certainly eye-catching and thought-provoking, as there are some appealing parts.

For instance, there is a rhetorical question, which is the following-“What immortal hand or eye could frame thy fearful symmetry?”. This line completely expresses the whole idea of the poem. The line also points out the idea that, if God created the fearsome tiger, what kind of creator he is.

There is no doubt that the rhetorical question is particularly addressed to the tiger.

However, during the whole poem it should be felt that the tiger becomes less and less present becoming more and more an object of the speaker’s own fierce contemplation.

Another catchy line of the poem is the last question which is similar to the first one. That is as follows-> “What immortal hand or eye dare frame thy fearful symmetry”.

It is quite obvious that there is a slight difference between those two rhetorical questions. Here it is worth to note the words could and dare, that differentiate the two ideas.

The second question can be observed as the culmination of the speaker’s questions about God. It addresses the tiger only in form. Actually the question is addressed to God himself.

By marking the difference in those lines, the speaker probably has a lot to say.

Before reading the poem the first thing that came to my mind was the tiger itself with its beauty, dangerousness and of course attractiveness.

After reading the poem, I immediately imagined God as I realized most of the words expressed by the author are directly addressed to God, the nature of God’s creation.

It should be supposed that the entire poem is specifically about how the nature of God’s creation can be conformed with the existence of the fearsome tiger.

Everything about the creation of the tiger simply suggests effort, skill and artistry.

An attractive and worth considering phrase of the poem is “burning bright”. This phrase definitely outlines the beauty and charm of the tiger. It has to say that despite the fact that the tiger is incredibly charming, it is also terribly fearful.

The phrase “burning bright” creates the visual image of a flash of appealing colour moving through the “forests of the night”-> It should be concluded that tiger and forest are both beautiful and terrifying.

The image that immediately came to my mind after reading the poem is the image of fire. Tiger is like a burning fire, that catches everybody’s attention.

As dawn breaks, light shines upon the still life before us,

The quiet mumble of the glistening water,
And even the rocks, who never speak, are glowing,
The townspeople awoken to a new day...

By Me

Varosyan Mariam

William Blake (The Tyger)

Tyger Tyger, **burning bright**,
In the forests of the **night**
What immortal hand or eye,
Could frame thy fearful **symmetry**?
In what distant deeps or skies.
Burnt the fire of thine eyes?
On what wings dare he aspire?
What the hand, dare seize the fire?

.....

William Blake's, "The Tyger", is the poetic counterpart to the Lamb of Innocence from his previous

work, Songs of Innocence, thus creating the expression of innocence versus experience "What immortal hand or eye / Dare frame thy fearful symmetry. "The Tyger" is part of the continued series of lyrics titled Songs of Experience that was published in 1794, as a response to the Songs of Innocence. The Songs of Experience are interpreted as the child, conveyed in Songs of Innocence, matures to adulthood and is molded by the harsh experiences and negative forces that reality has on human life, thus shows the destructiveness of the tiger. Blake uses "tyger" instead of tiger because it refers to any kind of wild, ferocious cat.

I really liked the poem it was very interesting and original. When i first read the title, my ideas were a little different. Although it was clear from the title what would be described. When i first read the title i imagined a dark forest that would be home to many homeless animals and where many mysterious realities would take place.

Siranush Hovhannisyan

Heavenly

You're the stairway to my heart
So powerful and strange, that
I think you're the song
Which I hear when I'm stormed
And I calm down.
I think you're the song
That I hear when I'm torn
And I get strong.
And I think you're the song
That when my guard is down,

Makes me cry, makes me calm
Makes me live when I'm dead,
Lights the bulb in my head,
Raises my hopes to go ahead.
You're so wonderful and strange,
That I think you're the song
Which I hear when I live
Which I hear just to live
You're the stairway to my heaven.
Gohar Galoyan

Talking about the William Blake's poetry we are hit by the wave of romanticism. One can find it in his

works. One of those works is “The Lamb”. This stresses importance for me because in this world of negativity and dishonesty we can find light and tenderness in a single verse. The author's preference of words used in the song is perfect: delight, softest, bright, tender, rejoice etc. So we can associate these words with holy purity. The presence of the holy spirit is evidently visible in the second part of the verse. Here are some lines that can prove this.

"He is called by thy name,
For he calls himself a Lamb,
We are called by his name."

So here the lamb is identified with God, and that's why the Lamb is written in a capital letter. To me these words are of great importance because it is to say the lamb is the innocence, God is in the lamb, so we can find innocence by following God. We can also find child's character between the lines which is identified with the innocence as well.

The author uses "thee" instead of "you" so we can consider that the monologue is with a child, because “thee” is an informal way to call someone.

PS. The image of the Lamb is also shown in the Bible, this once more proves the holiness of the animal.

After hearing the students' answer, it is advisable to deliver additional information on the question that was not answered. Let us take the question of English Romanticism as a vivid example.

Additional information: Emboldened by the era's revolutionary spirit, Romantic poets invented new lit-

erary forms to match. Romantic poetry can argue radical ideas explicitly and vehemently (as in Percy Bysshe Shelley's “England in 1819,” a sonnet in protest of Peterloo) or allegorically and ambivalently (as in William Blake's “The Tyger,” from *Songs of Innocence and of Experience*). To quote from William Wordsworth's preface to *Lyrical Ballads*, the groundbreaking collection he wrote with fellow poet-critic Samuel Taylor Coleridge, Romantic poets could “choose incidents and situations from common life” as its subjects, describing them not in polished or high-flown diction but instead in everyday speech, “a selection of language really used by men.” Romanticism can do justice to the disadvantaged, to those marginalized or forgotten by an increasingly urban and commercial culture—rural workers, children, the poor, the elderly, or the disabled—or it can testify to individuality simply by foregrounding the poet's own subjectivity at its most idiosyncratic or experimental. (<https://www.poetryfoundation.org/collections/152982/an-introduction-to-british-romanticism>)

The flow of questions may vary conditioned by the atmosphere of the auditorium. Focus should be paid on the literary studies as well.

1. What figures of speech are dominant in Blake's poetry?
2. What similarities would you mention in W. Blake's, W. Wordsworth's and Armenian Romantic poets?

Lake District internet-based photo

As a new lesson, question/answer format is preferable.

Who is William Wordsworth?

A key figure in the English Romantic movement, Wordsworth combined mystical nature worship with concern for the lives of the rural poor. His use of the 'real language of men' had a lasting influence on English verse.

How can we introduce Wordsworth's key works chronologically?

Siranush: The format question/answer during literature classes are highly effective, especially in understanding and analysing special ideas, concepts in poems. Questions make students think about the matter they concentrate their mental power on finding the "perfect" answer. As a result of it the key terms, definitions, special characteristics and the authors become well discussed and understood. It also leads to personal conclusions.

Lilit: I guess it is quite an effective way to study poetry in that way. As we know poetry covers various topics - writers' biographies, poems and their analysis, stories and etc. And due to the technique "question - answer exchange " it seems possible to focus on a particular topic that you are mostly interested in. Questions help to make our brains work and develop critical thinking. Also questions promote to go deep in certain topics and study them properly.

Julia: Of course, the first and the most important part of learning something is the questions. Questions help you to know whatever you want, or maybe you

know something but you are uncertain. To study English poetry questions is also useful, for example you can ask question and understand the whole meaning what you studying. So question are the fasy way to get answers.

Syuzi: There is no doubt in my mind that a quite productive and useful Question/ answer technique is promotable while learning poetry. This is an effective technique which assures that students will have to do some of their own discovering and at the same time it helps them to underline the main aspects and crucial features of the work they are focusing on, In addition to this, it is definitely helpful for developing their independent thinking, realisation and of course imagination.

To sum up, the teachers should use questions properly as an effective tool that promotes classroom interaction, enhances students' communicative competence, and makes the learning process of poetic texts more efficient.

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